

Craft-Based Data-Physicalization Workshop 2026 - Submission

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Statement: I have been cultivating an interest for the making of data-sculptures and “dataphys” for seven years. I started with a research and creation notebook (<https://datartefacts.hypotheses.org/>), exploring various ways of making data-physicalizations with clay & ceramics, while conducting interviews with makers as well. I don't have any expert-level craft skills, I am more interested in the conceptual reflection, the exploration of various encoding methods, as well as the study of historical data-physicalizations. I explore various crafts, techniques and materials to make objects, all remaining relatively simple and accessible.

I currently have three main documented projects related to craft:

- one is the **Flood Necklace** (1) (completed in 2021), a 3 meters long oversized “necklace” with ceramic spheres of various sizes, which diameters represent the water heights of each flood recorded for the Loire river (France) in Orleans between 1800 and 2003. The two top values of the series are the white spheres (1856 and 1866), which led to major infrastructure construction in France to regulate floods. It would be interesting to consider adding the 2026 floods to the piece.
- the second project is an oversize **Demographic Khipus** (2.5 meters wide by 1.3 meters high) embedding the demographic evolution of the Inka population from the year 1200 to 1600 (from the rise of the empire to its fall). This project uses a simple set of ropes and strings, with wood beads instead of knots, and follows the data encoding system of traditional khipus on a 10 basis. Data come from a mathematical model, since experts don't have precise records of the population evolution for that period. Data have been adjusted so the number encoded per vertical rope needs to be multiplied by 60 000 to get the accurate number of people for that year. This was to make the project fit with material constraints (number of beads required, weight, size).
- the third project is called **the Tilt**, and is about using analog photography techniques as a graphical method to make a bar chart. It basically uses light to encode light-related data. The longer the exposure to light, the darker the paper gets. The project is called “The Tilt” (2) and represents the average daylight time per month (12 values per image) for 6 different cities from the 75e parallel north to the Equator. The final project features 6 images (one per city), each embedding 12 values (one bar per month), showing how the seasonal variations of night and day time are influenced by the Earth's tilt.

- (1) The making of the Flood Necklace is documented here: <https://datartefacts.hypotheses.org/450> as well as in a presentation I gave about the valorization of river's historical data here: <https://datartefacts.hypotheses.org/2312>
- (2) The Tilt was presented during a Data + Women Zurich talk online here about dataphysicalization and photography: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=LR8moNOnUCk&t=936s>

Fig. 1: The Flood Necklace (2021) - Ceramics & Rope.

Fig. 2: Demographic khipus - This khipus encodes the demographic evolution between 1200 and 1600 of the Inca population, inventors of the khipus. Beads in the upper section are thousands. Beads in the mid-section are hundreds. Beads in the lower section are units. The numbers are in a 60 000 base for scale purposes. The

red yarn on the left indicates the reading direction. As khipus were usually rolled in balls for transportation, there was a need to indicate the reading direction directly on the object itself, usually under the form of a yarn or textile pom-pom. Here, the starting point is the oldest data at the left (year 1200), progressing towards the right to the most recent data (year 1600).

Fig 3. Close up on the demographic khipu.

Fig. 4: Final results of “The Tilt”: six sheets of photographic paper, each encoding the 12 months data of daylight per month (from January to December) for a different city, from Nordic latitudes to the equator. The two left images represent Nordic latitudes daylight variations during the year (the black bars representing winter months, the light bars representing the long days of the summer). The two center images represent cities located mid-hemisphere (where variations of daylight are still observable between winter and summer), the last two images on the right represent cities close to the equator, where daylight time is very similar all year long.

Fig 5 (left): view of the enlarger in the photo lab, used to encode the light data into photographic paper. Fig 6 (right): view of the opaque cache made for the purpose of realising “The Tilt” project.